
Health problems of women labours in the field of grape: A Sociological study

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Abstract

The present sociological study examines the health problems faced by women labourers working in grape farms in Tasgaon taluka of Sangli district, Maharashtra. Using fieldwork and survey methods, data were collected from 120 women workers and 4 doctors to understand their working conditions, lifestyle, and occupational health issues. Findings reveal that women workers perform long hours of labour-intensive tasks and are exposed to harmful chemicals such as gibberellic acid, pesticides, and especially hydrogen cyanide during grape processing. Most workers are illiterate and lack access to protective equipment, health awareness, and social security measures. A significant proportion suffer from skin diseases, allergies, infections, and other health complications related to chemical exposure. The study highlights the urgent need for improved workplace safety, health education, and institutional support for women grape workers.

Keywords: Women labourers, Grape farming, Occupational health, Chemical exposure, Hydrogen cyanide, Work conditions, Skin diseases, Maharashtra, Sociological study.

Introduction

Swami Vivekananda had said “that country and that nation which did not respect women have never become great nor will ever in future.” Now a days whole world tries to empower the status of women not only in socially, but also with the reference of health, occupational ,equality, politics and cultural perspectives. Women work and health with the reference of occupational hazards is another important issue in present modern society. The working conditions of women workers posed them many health hazards. Studies have revealed that our women themselves are neglecting their own health. Normally Indian women consume less food and spend more energy on work. As S. C. Dube pointed out there three principal areas in which controls are exercised on women : (1) women ‘s sexuality is controlled much more strictly then men’s (2) there are restriction on women’s movements and contacts., (3) women’s resources (labor and skills) need regulation and control. Grape is an important commercial fruit crop of Maharashtra state in India having vast export. The state ranks first in respect of area (70,000 hectares) of production (1650000 MT) and the productivity (28MT/ha) of grapes in the country. Grape agriculture is the fourth largest fruit crop in Maharashtra occupying 12 percent of horticultural area at 17000 hectors. Mostly Nashik and Tasgaon taluka in Sangli district are well known for the grapes. This research paper

attempts to study the Health problems of women labours in the field of grape

Objectives of the study

1. To study the working conditions of women grape workers.
2. To understand the lifestyle of women grape workers.
3. To find out the health-related problems of women grape workers.
4. To find out the diseases mostly common in the women grape workers.

Research Methodology

The researcher has used the field work method and survey research method for this study. The descriptive research design has been used for this particular study.

The Sampling Design:

The researcher has chosen 120 women workers from four villages of Tasgaon taluka of Sangali district, Maharashtra with the use of purposive sampling method. data has been also collected from 4 Doctors of these villages with the use of interview schedule. Survey and observation method has been used for primary data collection about the work condition on the other hand interview scheduled used for health problems of women grape workers.

In this particular study researcher focused on present status, how working conditions and health problems related with the live of grape workers.

Scope and limitations of study:

This study is related only with the women workers and their work conditions. this study is limited only for grapes farm workers. It also covers the health problems of women's during their work.

Findings and conclusions:**Working conditions and present situation of women workers:**

1. All women workers do work for 8 to 9 hours in a day. They got 200 to 250 rupees for this work.
2. They do all kinds of work related with the grapes farm. i.e. Cultivation of trees, cutting the grapes trees etc.
3. All (100%) women workers do the contact with same chemicals of grapes, i.e. Gibberellic acid, Hydrogen Cyanide, some kinds of pesticides.
4. All (100%) women workers do the contact with the Hydrogen Cyanide for a one and half month (October and November) in one year.
5. They goes on farm for work with the group of 8-10 women's but women grape workers have not any union in that particular village.
6. Majority 67% of women workers are illiterate and 33% women workers have studied only up to elementary level.
7. Most of women are from 40 to 50 years old age group.

Health Problems:

1. 80% chemicals and pesticides are very dangers for human being.
2. Hydrogen Cyanide is a very harmful chemical for human being.
3. Majority of women's (60%) have the health problems.
4. Majority of women workers have skin problems due to the cause of hydrogen cyanide.
5. 80% of women workers take tobacco in the working period.
6. If any men / women contacts with the alcohol during the use of hydrogen cyanide, they suffers from allefies, dangers problems, infection, painfull rashes etc.
7. When they have a problem due to hydrogen cyanide then he/she cannot do any self work for 10 to 15 days, because of major skin diseases.
8. There is no any availability of hand gloves or any other facility of skin care.
9. There is no facility of insurance about these women workers.

Recommendations

1. Increase research on how health-related problems impact the lives of farm workers.
2. To increase the level of awareness towards the health issues of workers especially women workers.
3. Women workers should establish the union.
4. Every grape farmer should have information about the pesticides and other all chemicals that they use.

5. Wearing protective hand gloves and mask can help prevent the contact of chemicals to skin.

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